

Subject 1: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis on Risk Factors for Sporadic Food-Borne Illnesses

Part III: Shigatoxin-producing *Escherichia coli* infection

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The quality assessment stage was passed by 29 primary studies investigating only sporadic STEC infection, which were conducted between 1986 and 2013. Fourteen studies investigated pathways of exposure in children and twenty in the mixed population. Whereas 297 ORs (61% of the data) originated from exposures evaluated in the mixed population, 196 ORs (39%) were quantified from ill children cases. The Children population class was further broken down into two non-mutually exclusive categories: Young children (70 ORs), comprising infants and children up to 6 years old; and Older Children (126 ORs), comprising children up to 16 years of age. These primary studies provided 503 ORs categorised for meta-analysis, being 80% of the meta-analytical data produced by case-control studies from USA (8), Canada (5), USA (4), Argentina (2), Australia (2) and Germany (1). Nineteen case-control studies (56%) employed a matched experimental design and produced a total of 320 ORs. Three-hundred and fifty-nine reported ORs were not adjusted by any confounder, while 134 ORs were adjusted by using either Mantel-Haenzel method or logistic regressions. The models used to calculate the crude or adjusted OR were evenly distributed among chi-square (133 ORs), Mantel-Haenzel (143 ORs), unconditional logistic (92 ORs) and conditional logistic (125 ORs). After methodological quality assessment, five case-control studies were marked as being below standards, which yielded a total of 69 potentially-biased ORs. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused more on the multiple pathways of exposure (477 ORs) than on host specific factors (7 ORs) and travel (9 ORs).

According to this meta-analysis study, the most important routes of STEC infection, apart from international travel (overall OR=3.50; 95% CI: 0.99 – 12.35) and domestic travel (overall OR=3.03; 95% CI: 0.96 – 9.54), were: consumption of poultry meat (overall OR=3.03; 95% CI: 1.79 – 6.35), living on a farm (overall OR=2.67; 95% CI: 2.18 – 3.27) and

person-to-person contagion (overall OR=2.57; 95% CI: 1.44 – 4.59). Some environmental or animal routes of exposure, namely, occupational contact with animals (overall OR=2.48; 95% CI: 1.22 – 5.02), untreated drinking water (overall OR=2.21; 95% CI: 1.68 – 2.89), and contact with farm animals (overall OR=2.11; 95% CI: 1.21 – 3.71) bore higher association with STEC disease in the mixed population than consumption of beef (overall OR=1.94; 95% CI: 1.46 – 2.59) or other non-specific meats (overall OR=2.01; 95% CI: 1.43 – 2.81). After beef, other important routes of exposure to STEC in the mixed population were: recent use of antibiotics (overall OR=1.77; 95% CI: 1.09 – 2.88), meat-based RTE foods (overall OR=1.77; 95% CI: 1.43 – 2.18), handling of manure and bush camping (overall OR=1.71; 95% CI: 1.17 – 2.51), fast foods (overall OR=1.62; 95% CI: 0.97 – 2.72), contact with pets (overall OR=1.59; 95% CI: 0.82 – 3.08), fish (overall OR=1.55; 95% CI: 0.87 – 2.75), processed meats (overall OR=1.53; 95% CI: 1.11 – 2.10), BBQ meats (overall OR=1.52; 95% CI: 1.00 – 2.29), composite dishes (overall OR=1.43; 95% CI: 0.95 – 2.16), cheese (overall OR=1.36; 95% CI: 0.68 – 2.74), fruits (overall OR=1.34; 95% CI=1.09 – 1.64) and recreational water (overall OR=1.31; 95% CI: 1.00 – 1.71).

In older children, the highest association with STEC infection were posed by person-to-person transmission (overall OR=4.55; 95% CI: 1.98 – 10.43) and contact with farm animals (overall OR=3.25; 95% CI: 2.38 – 4.44). The food categories of multi-ingredient dishes (overall OR=2.88; 95% CI: 1.24 – 6.72), beef (overall OR=2.21; 95% CI: 1.58 – 3.08) and other non-specific meats (overall OR=2.11; 95% CI: 1.20 – 3.20) were more important sources of STEC disease than the environmental pathways of living on a farm (overall OR=1.69; 95% CI: 1.35 – 2.12) and drinking untreated water (overall OR=1.61; 95% CI: 1.18 – 2.21). Other important food vehicles of transmission of STEC in older children, after beef, were meat-based RTE foods (overall OR=1.95; 95% CI: 1.42 – 2.67), processed meats (overall OR=1.51; 95% CI: 0.87 – 2.63) and raw milk (overall OR=1.40; 95% CI: 0.69 – 2.86).

In young children, the top three determinants of STEC infection were living on a farm (overall OR=5.34; 95% CI: 2.51 – 11.36), contact with farm animals (overall OR=4.36; 95% CI: 2.47 – 7.69) and person-to-person contagion (overall OR=3.12; 95% CI: 1.18 – 8.21). Person-to-person and farm environment/animals were also two of the most important sources of STEC in older children and the mixed population. Contrarily to what was found for older children and the mixed population, beef (overall OR=1.20; 95% CI: 0.89 – 1.63) was not an important vehicle of transmission of STEC. Food classes that bore higher risk of infection were raw milk (overall OR=2.76; 95% CI: 0.79 – 9.65), other non-specific meats (overall OR=2.57; 95% CI: 1.44 – 4.60), processed meats (overall OR=1.83; 95% CI: 1.09 – 3.07) and composite dishes (overall OR=1.36; 95% CI: 0.86 – 2.14). Other equally relevant environmental sources of STEC in young children were: exposure to playground (overall OR=2.50; 95% CI: 1.57 – 3.99) and recreational water (overall OR=1.74; 95% CI: 1.04 – 2.93).

Other meta-analysis models were adjusted to estimate the effects of food handling (raw/undercooked) and setting (home/eating out) on the mean ORs in selected food classes. It was found that people who ate raw or undercooked beef/minced beef/other meats had on average 1.466 times (95% CI: 1.219 – 1.766) greater probability of acquiring STEC infection than those who (stated having) consumed *simply* beef. Drinking non-pasteurised milk also conveyed an increased risk of disease by 2.002 times (95% CI: 1.080 – 3.709) that of the base scenario. Eating foods prepared outside the home did not appear to increase the risk of

becoming infected with STEC, as shown by the non-significant OR(Eating out)/OR(base scenario) ratios from consuming beef/minced beef/other meats (1.108; 95% CI: 0.897 – 1.368) and processed meats (0.712; 95% CI: 0.428 – 1.184).

Routes of exposure that on meta-analysis had weak (pooled OR marginally higher than one) or non-significant association with STEC infection were: dairy-based RTE (overall OR=1.27; 95% CI: 0.75 – 2.10), milk (overall OR=1.22; 95% CI: 0.74 – 2.02), vegetables (overall OR=1.17; 95% CI: 0.81 – 1.67) and pork meat (overall OR=0.81; 95% CI: 0.48 – 1.37) in the mixed population; attending day care (overall OR=1.25; 95% CI: 0.73 – 2.15), consumption of fruits (overall OR=0.98; 95% CI: 0.59 – 1.63) and vegetables (overall OR=0.84; 95% CI: 0.56 – 1.27) in older children; and contact with pets (overall OR=1.06; 95% CI: 0.72 – 1.56) and consumption of red meats other than beef (overall OR=1.00; 95% CI: 0.63 – 1.59) in young children. Although powder infant formula presented a relatively high mean risk (overall OR=1.61) in young children, its significance as an important vehicle of STEC could not be proven (95% CI: 0.31 – 8.42). Very limited data were available for the food subcategories of seafood, eggs, grains and beverages, so the significance of these sources as potential vehicles of transmission of STEC could not be appraised.

3. Results

3.3 Shigatoxin-producing *Escherichia coli*

3.3.1 *Descriptive statistics*

In the systematic review of risk factors pertaining to human infection with STEC, a total of 4718 bibliographic sources were identified using the keywords in the five search engines, from which only 134 passed the full assessment for eligibility comprising case-control and case-case studies from both sporadic illnesses and outbreaks (Figure 1). A total of 105 fully-documented case-control studies investigated the source(s) of outbreaks and were kept in the JabRef file as their data can be readily extracted. In this study, meta-analysis was undertaken using 29 primary studies focused on sporadic disease (Figure 1). These published studies were conducted between 1986 and 2013. Table 1 compiles a list of the case-control studies along with their main features.

The eligible studies jointly provided 503 categorised odds-ratios for meta-analysis. A total of 213 ORs were retrieved from 17 case-control studies performed before the year 2000, while 280 ORs were excerpted from 12 case-control studies performed after 2000. The majority of primary studies investigated STEC infection or HUS caused by undifferentiated strains (9 case-control studies), O157:H7 (12 studies) and O157 (7 studies), producing 83.5% of the meta-analytical data (Figure 2, top right). The countries whose case-control studies presented the largest body of results for sporadic STEC infection were USA (8), Canada (5), USA (4), Argentina (2), Australia (2) and Germany (1), which produced all together ~80% of the ORs retrieved (Figure 2, top left). Fourteen studies investigated pathways of exposure in children and twenty in the mixed population; however, these case-control studies do not add up to the total number of 29, because five of them presented separate results for the mixed and the children population. Those were Friesema et al. (2015), Kassenborg et al. (2004), Pierard et al. (1999), Voetsch et al. (2007) and Werber et al. (2007). Whereas 297 ORs (61% of the data) originated from exposures evaluated in the mixed population, 196 ORs (39%) were quantified from ill children cases. The Children category was further broken down into two categories: “Young children” (70 ORs), comprising infants and children up to 6 years old; and “Older Children” (126 ORs), comprising children up to 16 years of age. It is important to bear in mind that the children population categories are not mutually exclusive (Figure 2, bottom left). As a rule, because of their distinct routes of exposure, the ORs for children and mixed populations were not joined in a single meta-analysis model, but in separate meta-analyses. Data from both age groups were merged only when the ORs belonging to the children population were too few to run a separate meta-analysis model.

In twenty-six primary studies, the STEC infections were laboratory-confirmed, while in three studies (Cieslak et al., 1997; Gianviti et al., 1994; and Locking et al. 2001), there was no indication that all of the cases were confirmed. Nineteen case-control studies (56%) employed a matched experimental design and produced a total of 320 categorised ORs. While 47 ORs were computed in multivariate analysis, 273 were obtained in univariate analysis. ORs from matched designs were mostly estimated using MH (143) and CL (125) and some of them by UL (10) and the simple chi-square test (42). From the case-control studies that used an unmatched or frequency-matched design (13 studies), 139 ORs were computed in univariate analysis while 34 in multivariate analysis. The ORs from unmatched designs were estimated using chi-square (91) and UL (82). Bringing together the matched and unmatched designs,

359 of the extracted ORs were not adjusted by any confounder (crude ORs), while only 134 ORs were adjusted using either MH or logistic regressions.

Figure 1. Flow chart of literature search for case-control studies of STEC infection
*Records kept in JabRef with PDFs files annexed

During methodological quality assessment, five case-control studies were marked as being possibly affected by selection bias. In Rivero et al. (2011) and Bryant et al. (1989), controls had diarrhoea caused by other gastrointestinal infections. Likewise, in Byrne and Jenkins

(2014) and Wang et al. (2013), controls were not well individuals but patients with STEC O157 infections. As it is not clear whether these controls shared routes of exposure with the case patients, the ORs extracted from these studies were marked as having potential for bias. Finally, the OR measures from Rivas et al. (2008) were assigned the potential-for-bias status because although they used a matched design, from the data presented in the article, only crude ORs could be calculated (as opposed to MH- or CL- estimates which would have been more appropriate to the design). These five case-control studies provided 69 potentially-biased ORs whose influence on the meta-analysed OR estimates was appraised by means of the Cook's distance. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused much more on the multiple pathways of transmission (477 ORs) than on host specific factors (7 ORs) or travel (9 ORs) (Figure 3). General information on the distribution of the number of ORs available for meta-analysis is presented in Figure 3 by study design, type of analysis, model, type of odds-ratio, case definition and potential for bias status.

Figure 2. Distribution of the number of odds-ratios (y-axis) extracted from case-control studies of sporadic human infection with STEC by country (top left), pathotype (top right) population type (bottom left) and type of risk factor (bottom right)

Figure 3. Pie-diagrams of the number of odds-ratios extracted from case-control studies of sporadic infections with STEC by design (top left), analysis type (top right), model type (middle left), odds-ratio type (middle right), case definition (bottom left) and assigned potential for bias (bottom right)

Table 1. Characteristics of case-control studies included in the meta-analysis

Study ID	Country	Study period	Population	Design	Analysis & model*	# cases/controls	Quality Final ORs /removed
Belongia et al. 2003	USA	1997-1999	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	86 O157:H7 525 controls	Good 14
Bielaszewska et al. 1997	Czech Republic	1995	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	15 O157:HUS 45 controls	Good 1
Bryant et al. 1989	Canada	1986-1987	Mixed	Matched	Uni-Chi	49 O157:H7 49 controls	Good 9
				Unmatched	Uni-Chi	81 O157:H7 96 other GI	Poor 7
Byrne et al. 2014	UK	2009-2012	Mixed	Matched	Multi-CL	67 Non-O157 2300 O157	Poor 1
Cieslak et al. 1997	USA	1993	Mixed	Matched	Uni-CL	10 O157:H7 15 control	Good 2
Denno et al. 2009	USA	2003-2005	Children	Matched	Uni-CL	39 O157:H7 78 controls	Good 5
Friesema et al. 2015	Netherlands	2008-2012	Children	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	39 O157 15 non-O157	Good 28
			Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	91 O157 63 non-O157 1563 controls	
Gianviti et al. 1994	Italy	1988-1992	Children	Matched	Multi-UL	43 HUS 43 controls	Good 1
Heusinkveld et al. 2016	Netherlands	2013-2014	Children	Unmatched	Multi-UL	27 STEC 937 controls	Good 1
Holton et al. 1999	Canada	1991	Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH Multi-CL	100 O157:H7 200 controls	Good 10
Hundy 2004	Australia	2002	Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH	11 STEC 22 controls	Good 11/1
Jaros et al. 2013	New Zealand	2011-2012	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	113 STEC 506 controls	Good 26
Kassenborg et al. 2004	USA	1996-1997	Mixed Children	Matched	Uni-CL Multi-CL	196 O157:H7 372 controls	Good 12
LeSaux et al. 1993	Canada	1990	Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH	110 O157:H7 220 controls	Good 5
Locking et al. 2001	UK	1996-1999	Mixed	Matched	Uni-CL Multi-CL	183 O157:HUS 545 controls	Good 38/1
MacDonald et al. 1988	USA	1985-1986	Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH	24 O157:H7 48 controls	Good 1
McPherson et al. 2009	Australia	2003-2007	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	43 O157 71 non-O157 304 controls	Good 48
Mead et al. 1997	USA	1994	Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH,CL	22 O157:H7 44 controls	Good 16
O'Brien et al. 2001	UK	1996-1997	Mixed	Unmatched	Multi-UL	369 O157 511 controls	Good 8

Parry et al. 1998	UK	1994-1996	Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH Multi-CL	85 O157 142 controls	Good 29/1
Pierard et al. 1999	Belgium	1998	Children	Matched	Uni-MH	29 O157 55 controls	Good 25/1
			Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH	21 eaeA-pos 40 controls	
			Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH	16 eaeA-pos 29 controls	
			Mixed	Matched	Multi-CL	37 STEC 69 controls	
Rivas et al. 2008	Argentina	2001-2002	Children	Matched	Uni-CL Multi-CL	150 STEC 299 controls	Poor 62/1
					Uni-Chi	58 O157 116 controls	
					Uni-Chi	38 non-O157 75 controls	
Rivero et al. 2011	Argentina	2010	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	62 STEC/HUS 372 other GI	Poor 24/1
Rowe et al. 1993	Canada	1990	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	34 HUS 102 controls	Good 8
Slutsker et al. 1998	USA	1990-1992	Mixed	Matched	Uni-CL	73 O157:H7 142 controls	Good 10/1
Vaillant et al. 2009	France	2000-2001	Children	Matched	Uni-MH Multi-CL	105 HUS 196 controls	Good 13
Voetsch et al. 2007	USA	1999-2000	Mixed Children	Matched	Multi- UL/CL	179 STEC adults 104 STEC child 534 controls	Good 17
Wang et al. 2013	Canada	2009-2011	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	63 non-O157 154 O157/HUS	Poor 4
Werber et al. 2007	Germany	2001-2003	Children	Matched	Uni-MH Multi-CL	145 STEC child 145 controls	Good 57/4
			Mixed	Matched	Uni-MH Multi-CL	57 STEC adults 57 controls	

(*) Univariate analysis can be univariate (Uni) and multivariate (Model) while model can be chi-square (Chi), Mantel-Haenzel (MH), unconditional logistic (UL) and conditional logistic (CL)

3.3.2 *Meta-analysis for host-specific risk factors and travel-, environment-, animal- and food-related pathways of transmission*

The meta-analyses performed on the different data partitions showed that, in recent years (after 2000), some exposures gained importance in the transmission of STEC infection. This is true for the animal-contact pathways ($p=0.003$; Table 4B) in the older children population, since case-control studies conducted after 2000 produced significantly higher ORs than the older case-control studies did. In the mixed population, however, there was no noticeable effect of study period on the measured ORs for most of the risk factors and exposure pathways, except for the consumption of dairy food ($p=0.078$; Table 9B) and RTE foods ($p=0.004$; Table 13B), whereby the overall risk of STEC was found to increase in more recent

years. Said otherwise, in the mixed population, dairy and RTE foods began to be ascertained as determinants of STEC infections only recently.

Although there were not many ORs related to travel as risk factor available in the literature, the meta-analysis by geographical region was still performed. It revealed that travel was overall a significant risk factor, with pooled ORs ranging between 1.719 and 6.462 (Table 2A). On average, people who travelled recently had 2.793 (95% CI: 1.530– 5.104) greater probability of getting infected with STEC than people who did not travel at all (Table 2B). For nationals of UK and Canada, travelling abroad increased their odds of infection with STEC by an average of 3.497 (95% CI: 0.990 – 12.36). Domestic travelling represented a lower risk at an overall OR of 3.028 (95% CI: 0.961 – 9.544), as meta-analysed from nationals of USA and UK (Table 2B). The meta-analysis conducted on the travel data partition suggested the likely presence of publication bias ($p=0.035$), although its respective funnel plot showed an acceptable spread of observations, particularly considering the few OR measures available in this partition (Figure 4). No potentially-biased OR was removed after assessing influential observations by Cook's distance.

Table 2A. Meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for STEC infection by geographical region for the combined mixed (n=6 ORs) and children (n=3 ORs) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed and Children					
North America	1.866	0.424	3	[1.034 – 2.697]	<.0001
North Europe	0.542	0.279	4	[-0.006 – 1.089]	0.053
South America	0.943	0.441	2	[0.078 – 1.807]	0.033

Table 2B. Meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for STEC infection for the combined mixed (n=6 ORs) and children (n=3 ORs) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All Travel (6 stud)	1.027	0.307	9	[0.425 – 1.630]	0.001
Fixed effects					
Travel abroad	1.252 ^b	0.644	3	[-0.010 – 2.515]	0.052
Travel inside	1.108 ^a	0.586	3	[-0.040 – 2.256]	0.059
Any travel	0.873 ^c	0.625	3	[-0.353 – 2.097]	0.162
Before 2000					0.258
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.7170	QE(df=6)		QM(df=3)	
s^2 (residual)	0.4890	p=0.017		p=0.048	
Publication bias	-0.0026	0.0012			0.035
Points removed	0				

Figure 4. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for STEC infection in combined mixed (n=6) and children (n=3 ORs) population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The meta-analysis on host-specific factors revealed that in both North America (pooled OR=5.883; p=0.003) and Oceania (pooled OR=1.768; p=0.022), the host-specific factors can exacerbate the risk of acquiring STEC infection (Table 3A). On average, people who had antibiotics or immunosuppressive medication presented 2.221 times (95% CI: 1.167 – 4.229) greater risk of acquiring STEC infection than those who did not take any of those medications (Table 3B). However, when the meta-analysis was conducted on the host-specific subcategories, it became more clear that the recent use of antibiotics is likely to have a lower association with disease (overall OR=1.768; 95% CI: 1.086 – 2.878), than the use of immunosuppressive medication (overall OR=5.883; 95% CI: 1.839 – 18.80). However, this is not conclusive by any means as the extracted ORs available for meta-analysis in this partition were too few. Publication bias was inferred from both the lack of effect of study size on the measured ORs (p=0.002), and the non-scattered distribution of observations within the funnel plot (Figure 5).

Table 3A. Meta-analyses of host specific factors for STEC infection by region for the mixed population (n=7)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	1.772	0.593	2	[0.609 – 2.934]	0.003
Oceania	0.570	0.248	5	[0.083 – 1.057]	0.022

Table 3B. Meta-analysis of host specific factors for STEC infection for the mixed population (n=7) – no geographical region removed

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
All host (3 stud)	0.798	0.328		[0.155 – 1.442]	0.015
Fixed effects					
Antibiotics	0.570 ^a	0.248	5	[0.083 – 1.057]	0.022
Immunosup	1.772 ^b	0.593	2	[0.609 – 2.934]	0.003
Before 2000					ND
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0291	QE(df=7)		QM(df=2)	
s^2 (residual)	0.2312	p=0.295		p=0.010	
Publication bias	0.0031	0.0017			0.002
Points removed	0				

Figure 5. Funnel plot of the meta-analyses of host-specific risk factors for STEC infection in the mixed population

Regarding the animal-related pathways of transmission in the mixed population, animal contact appeared to be overall an important source of STEC infection in the UK (North Europe, pooled OR=2.190, p=0.001) and Australia and New Zealand (Oceania, pooled OR=2.266, p=0.004 in Table 4A). In the Netherlands, Germany and Belgium (West Europe), contact with animals was not found to represent an important source of transmission in the mixed population (pooled OR=1.121; p=0.647 in Table 4A). By contrary, in Western European young (pooled OR=1.594; p=0.036) and older children (pooled OR=2.915; p<.0001), the association between animal contact and disease was significant. Likewise, in North America and South American children up to 16 years of age, having any contact with animal was a significant source of STEC infection (pooled OR=1.835; p<.0001; and pooled OR=3.380; p<.0001, respectively). For the general meta-analysis on animal contact by subcategories, no geographical region was removed.

Table 4A. Meta-analyses of pathways related to animal contact for STEC infection by region in the mixed population (n=32), young children (n=9) and older children (n=23)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North Europe	0.808	0.182	15	[0.444 – 1.156]	<.0001
Oceania	0.784	0.212	10	[0.368 – 1.200]	0.001
West Europe	0.114	0.249	7	[-0.370 – 0.603]	0.647
Young children					
West Europe	0.466	0.222	9	[0.030 – 0.901]	0.036
Older children					
North America	0.607	0.103	8	[0.405 – 0.809]	<.0001
South America	1.218	0.200	9	[0.824 – 1.612]	<.0001
West Europe	1.070	0.239	6	[0.606 – 1.539]	<.0001

On meta-analysis, STEC ill cases from the mixed population were 2.300 times (95% CI: 1.281 – 4.116; Table 4B) more likely to have had any contact with animals/raw meat than the controls. Within the mixed population, the occupational exposure, represented by working with livestock or in meat processing establishments (overall OR=2.476; 95% CI: 1.221 – 5.028), bears overall a comparable association with STEC infection as having direct contact with any farm animal (overall OR=2.115; 95% CI: 1.206 – 3.709). Yet, contact with farm animals poses a higher risk of infection with STEC in older children (pooled OR=3.248; 95% CI: 2.375 – 4.437), and even higher in young children (overall OR=4.358; 95% CI: 2.469 – 7.683). The occupational exposure to animals by a household member was not proven to be an important route of infection in children (overall OR=1.520; p=0.186). Despite the limited number of OR measures available for “contact with pets”, it is very likely for this route of exposure to be a less important determinant of STEC infections, either in the mixed population (overall OR=1.587; 95% CI: 0.818 – 3.077) or in young children (overall OR=1.059; 95% CI: 0.719 – 1.557; Table 4B). Applying the Cook’s distance diagnostics on the animal contact meta-analyses, one potentially-biased influential OR was removed from the mixed population data while none from the children data sets (Table 4B). In addition, there was no indication of strong potential bias in any of the meta-analyses (p=0.286 for the mixed population; p=0.263 for the young children population; and p=0.081 for the older children population; Table 4B), which was also suggested by the even dispersion of residuals in the three funnel plots (Figure 6).

Table 4B. Meta-analyses of pathways related to animal contact for STEC infection in the mixed population (n=32), young children (n=9) and older children (n=23) – no geographical region was removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (9 stud)	All animal	0.832	0.297	32	[0.248 – 1.415]	0.005
	Fixed effects					
	Farm	0.749 ^b	0.286	18	[0.188 – 1.311]	0.001
	Occupational	0.907 ^b	0.361	11	[0.200 – 1.615]	0.012
	Pets	0.462 ^a	0.338	3	[-0.201 – 1.124]	0.172
	Before 2000					0.618
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1934	QE(df=28)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3822	p=0.002		p=0.016	
	Publication bias	-0.0003	0.0003			0.286
Points removed	1					
Young children (3 stud)	All animal	0.466	0.222	9	[0.030 – 0.901]	0.036
	Fixed effects					
	Farm	1.472 ^b	0.289	4	[0.904 – 2.039]	<.0001
	Occupational*	0.419 ^a	0.317	2	[-0.202 – 1.041]	0.186
	Pets	0.057 ^a	0.197	3	[-0.330 – 0.443]	0.774
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=6)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.1204	p=0.772		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0008	0.0007			0.263
Points removed	0					
Older children (6 stud)	All animal	0.910	0.154	23	[0.609 – 1.212]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Farm	1.178	0.160	23	[0.865 – 1.490]	<.0001
	Before 2000	-0.562	0.189		[-0.933 – -0.192]	0.003
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=21)			
	s^2 (residual)	0.1573	p=0.951			
	Publication bias	-0.0010	0.0005			0.081
Points removed	0					

(*) Occupational exposure from household member

Figure 6. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of animal contact pathways as risk factors for STEC infection in the mixed population (top left), young children (top right) and older children (bottom). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

In general, the combined environmental pathways were strongly associated with STEC infection in the mixed population from North America (pooled OR=3.330, $p<.0001$), Northern Europe (pooled OR=1.608, $p<.0001$) and Oceania (pooled OR=2.166, $p<.0001$; Table 5A). Young children from North America (pooled OR=5.801; $p<.0001$) and Western Europe (pooled OR=1.786; $p<.0001$) were found to be more predisposed to STEC infections from environmental pathways than the mixed population. Although to a lesser degree than young children, older children from North America (pooled OR=1.719; $p<.0001$) and Western Europe (Germany and France, overall OR=1.443; $p=0.162$) were also prone to become infected with STEC from environmental pathways, bearing South American children the highest risk of disease (overall OR=3.564; $p<.0001$ in Table 5A). Thus, from the older children population, the OR data from South American studies were removed.

The general meta-analyses demonstrated the relevance of the environmental pathways as a whole in the transmission of STEC in the three population classes, with young children being more susceptible (overall OR=2.765; 95% CI: 1.290 – 5.918) than both older children (overall OR=1.685; 95% CI: 1.422 – 2.000) and the mixed population (overall OR=2.181; 95% CI: 1.758 – 2.713). On meta-analysis by environmental pathway, the mixed population in quotidian contact with farm environment (overall OR=2.702; 95% CI: 2.113 – 3.452) was

more exposed to STEC infection than those who drank untreated water (overall OR=2.206; 95% CI: 1.684 – 2.892; in Table 5B). At a significantly lower level of risk laid the environmental pathways of manure handling or bush camping (overall OR=1.714; 95% CI: 1.171 – 2.511) and recreational water (overall OR=1.306; 95% CI: 0.999 – 1.707) in the mixed population. Alike the mixed population, in young children, contact with farm environment was the most important environmental pathway of STEC transmission (overall OR=5.344; 95% CI: 2.514 – 11.35), followed by playing in a sandbox (playground; overall OR=2.504; 95% CI: 1.573 – 3.987) and recreational water (overall OR=1.742; 95% CI: 1.035 – 2.918). However, in older children, recreational water was found to have greater association with STEC infection (overall OR=6.814; 95% CI: 2.484 – 18.69) while untreated drinking water (overall OR=1.614; 95% CI: 1.179 – 2.212) and living on a farm (overall OR=1.694; 95% CI: 1.354 – 2.119) laid a lower level of risk, although still significant as sources of disease. Attending day care could not be proven to be an important pathway of contagion either in young children (overall OR=0.970; 95% CI: 0.540 – 1.744) or in older children (overall OR=1.250; 95% CI: 0.728 – 2.145 in Table 5B). After Cook’s distance assessment, no potentially-biased OR measure was removed from the meta-analyses (Table 5B). In addition, the OR measures appeared to be well distributed within the funnel plots from the meta-analyses of the three population classes (Figure 7). Publication bias was very unlikely since the measures of OR were not found to depend upon the case-control study size ($p=0.994$ for the mixed population; $p=0.857$ for young children; and $p=0.291$ for older children; Table 5B).

Table 5A. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for STEC infection by region for the mixed population (n=56), young children (n=12) and older children (n=20)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	1.203	0.165	13	[0.879 – 1.526]	<.0001
North Europe	0.475	0.079	20	[0.320 – 0.630]	<.0001
Oceania	0.773	0.069	23	[0.638 – 0.909]	<.0001
West Europe	-0.052	0.421	2	[-0.878 – 0.774]	0.908
Young children					
North America	1.758	0.435	2	[0.905 – 2.611]	<.0001
West Europe	0.580	0.149	10	[0.288 – 0.873]	<.0001
Older children					
North America	0.542	0.092	10	[0.361 – 0.722]	<.0001
South America	1.271	0.229	6	[0.823 – 1.719]	<.0001
West Europe	0.367	0.263	4	[-0.148 – 0.881]	0.162

Table 5B. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for STEC infection for the mixed population (n=56), young children (n=12) and older children (n=14) – South America removed from the older children population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (10 stud)	All environment	0.780	0.111	56	[0.564 – 0.998]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Drink water	0.791 ^c	0.138	13	[0.521 – 1.062]	<.0001
	Farm	0.983 ^c	0.104	25	[0.780 – 1.186]	<.0001
	Manure&Camp	0.539 ^b	0.195	5	[0.158 – 0.921]	0.006
	Rec. water	0.267 ^a	0.137	13	[-0.001 – 0.535]	0.051
	Before 2000					0.619
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0314	QE(df=52)		QM(df=4)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.3476	p=0.011		p<.0001	
Publication bias	0.0000	0.0003			0.994	
Points removed	0					
Young children (2 stud)	All environment	1.017	0.388	12	[0.255 – 1.778]	0.009
	Fixed effects					
	Day care	-0.030 ^a	0.299	2	[-0.616 – 0.556]	0.920
	Farm	1.676 ^d	0.385	3	[0.922 – 2.430]	<.0001
	Playground	0.918 ^c	0.237	3	[0.453 – 1.383]	<.0001
	Rec water	0.555 ^b	0.263	4	[0.035 – 1.071]	0.035
	Before 2000					0.689
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=8)		QM(df=4)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.2450	p=0.834		p<0.001	
Publication bias	-0.0004	0.0021			0.857	
Points removed	0					
Older children (5 stud)	All environment	0.522	0.087	14	[0.352 – 0.693]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Day care	0.223 ^a	0.276	3	[-0.318 – 0.763]	0.419
	Drink water	0.479 ^a	0.160	4	[0.165 – 0.794]	0.003
	Farm	0.527 ^a	0.114	5	[0.303– 0.751]	<.0001
	Rec water	1.919 ^b	0.515	2	[0.910 – 2.928]	<.0001
Before 2000					ND	

Random effects			
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=10)	QM(df=5)
s^2 (residual)	0.4675	p=0.012	p<0.001
Publication bias	-0.0007	0.0007	0.291
Points removed	0		

Figure 7. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of environmental pathways as risk factors for STEC infection in the mixed population (top left), young children (top right) and older children (bottom). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The contact with an ill person or a person having diarrhoea is another important source of transmission of STEC, confirmed – on meta-analysis – to have a significant OR measure of association in the North American (pooled OR=5.989; p<.0001), Western European (pooled OR=3.047; p=0.001) and Northern European (UK; pooled OR=2.085; p=0.081 in Table 6A). For the Argentinian results, person-to-person contagion in children and STEC had a weaker association (South America, pooled OR=1.701; p=0.131 in Table 6A). For this reason, the outcomes from the Argentinian case-control studies were removed for the subsequent general meta-analysis by population.

Table 6A. Meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of STEC by region for the combined mixed population (n=10), young children (n=4) and older children (n=12)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed and children (12 stud)					
North America	1.790	0.344	8	[1.115 – 2.465]	<.0001
North Europe	0.735	0.421	3	[-0.090 – 1.561]	0.081
South America	0.531	0.352	6	[-0.158 – 1.220]	0.131
West Europe	1.114	0.307	9	[0.512 – 1.715]	0.001

Table 6B. Meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of STEC for the combined mixed population (n=11), young children (n=3) and older children (n=7) – South America was removed

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects					
Older children	1.515 ^b	0.423	7	[0.685 – 2.345]	<.0001
Young children	1.137 ^a	0.494	3	[0.169 – 2.105]	0.021
Mixed	0.944 ^a	0.296	11	[0.364– 1.524]	0.001
Before 2000					0.096
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.3933	QE(df=18)		QM(df=3)	
s^2 (residual)	0.6974	p=0.004		p<.0001	
Publication bias	-0.0021	0.0009			0.016
Points removed	0				

Figure 8. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of STEC in the combined mixed population, young children and older children

On average, older children (overall OR=4.549; 95% CI: 1.984 – 10.43) and young children (overall OR=3.117; 95% CI: 1.184 – 8.207) presented a higher risk of acquiring STEC infection through person-to-person contagion than the mixed population (overall OR=2.570; 95% CI: 1.439 – 4.591 in Table 6B). In this data partition, no potentially-bias OR turned out to be an influential data point in the regression. The funnel plot (Figure 8) displayed a slight asymmetry; thus hinting some evidence of publication bias, which was also supported by the significant effect of study size on the measured ORs ($p=0.016$ in Table 6B).

Most of the routes of transmission of STEC infection recovered in the systematic review investigated exposures concerning consumption of food, for which a total of 282 OR measures were extracted and categorised. In the mixed population, the ingestion of foods was associated with acquiring STEC infection in the case-control studies from North America (pooled OR=1.707; $p<.0001$), Oceania (pooled OR=1.528; $p=0.028$) and Western Europe (pooled OR=1.636; $p=0.006$ in Table 7A). In the combined case-control studies from UK (Northern Europe), the association between contaminated food and STEC infection (pooled OR=1.076; $p=0.676$) was found to be only minor. Furthermore, South American young children were as exposed to STEC through food consumption (pooled OR=1.172; $p=0.074$) as Western European young children (pooled OR=1.244; $p=0.045$). For older children, food was more important a vehicle for transmission of STEC in South America (pooled OR=2.335; $p<.0001$) and Western Europe (pooled OR=1.962; $p<.0001$) than in North America (pooled OR=1.288; $p=0.080$ in Table 7A). No geographical region was removed for the meta-analysis on food by subcategory.

Table 7A. Meta-analyses of food pathways for STEC infection by region for the mixed population ($n=173$), young children ($n=45$) and older children ($n=64$)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.535	0.114	58	[0.312 – 0.759]	<.0001
North Europe	0.073	0.175	30	[-0.269 – 0.415]	0.676
Oceania	0.424	0.192	46	[0.047 – 0.801]	0.028
West Europe	0.492	0.179	39	[0.141 – 0.842]	0.006
Young children					
South America	0.159	0.085	22	[-0.015 – 0.332]	0.074
West Europe	0.218	0.109	23	[0.005 – 0.432]	0.045
Older children					
North America	0.253	0.145	10	[-0.031 – 0.537]	0.080
South America	0.848	0.079	36	[0.693 – 1.005]	<.0001
West Europe	0.674	0.126	18	[0.426 – 0.922]	<.0001

Table 7B. Meta-analyses of food pathways for STEC infection for for the mixed population (n=173), young children (n=39) and older children (n=63) – no region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (19 stud)	All foods	0.557	0.096	173	[0.369 – 0.745]	<.0001
	Fixed effects					
	Composite	0.557 ^c	0.234	15	[0.099 – 1.015]	0.017
	Dairy	0.176 ^a	0.254	12	[-0.321 – 0.673]	0.487
	Eggs	0.100 ^a	0.317	3	[-0.521 – 0.722]	0.752
	Meat	0.737 ^d	0.203	119	[0.338 – 1.136]	<.0001
	Produce	0.334 ^b	0.236	18	[-0.128 – 0.797]	0.156
	Seafood*	0.436 ^b	0.293	6	[-0.139 – 1.011]	0.137
	Before 2000					0.259
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.1918	QE(df=167)		QM(df=6)	
	s ² (residual)	0.5951	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0016	0.0003		<.0001	
Points removed	0					
Young children (5 stud)	All foods	0.260	0.076	39	[0.111 – 0.409]	0.001
	Fixed effects					
	Composite	0.304 ^b	0.232	3	[-0.152 – 0.760]	0.192
	Dairy	0.768 ^{ab}	0.498	10	[-0.208 – 1.744]	0.123
	Meat	0.372 ^b	0.138	21	[0.100 – 0.644]	0.007
	Produce	-0.191 ^a	0.213	5	[-0.609 – 0.227]	0.371
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.1540	QE(df=35)		QM(df=4)	
	s ² (residual)	0.6042	p=0.183		p=0.001	
	Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0008		0.745	
	Points removed	0				
	Older children (8 stud)	All foods	0.667	0.152	63	[0.369 – 0.965]
Fixed effects						
Composite		0.931 ^b	0.273	9	[0.396 – 1.466]	0.001
Dairy		0.331 ^b	0.359	3	[-0.374 – 1.035]	0.358
Meat		0.774 ^b	0.164	48	[0.452 – 1.096]	<.0001
Produce		-0.086 ^a	0.384	3	[-0.838 – 0.666]	0.823

Before 2000	ND		
Random effects			
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1260	QE(df=59)	QM(df=4)
s^2 (residual)	0.7398	p=0.001	p<.0001
Publication bias	0.0001	0.0008	0.899
Points removed	0		

(*) Only comprises fish

The general meta-analysis on food pathways demonstrated that food from assorted classes, could act as potential determinants of STEC infection (Table 7B). The overall risk of infection was slightly higher in older children (overall OR=1.948; 95% CI: 1.446 – 2.625) than in the mixed population (overall OR=1.745; 95% CI: 1.446 – 2.106); however, young children presented the lowest level of risk (overall OR=1.300; 95% CI: 1.117 – 1.505), which might stem from their lower consumption of “known potential sources of disease” such as undercooked meats (Table 7B). At this broader data partition, meta-analysis made it possible to establish which food categories were more or less associated with STEC infection. In the mixed population, dairy foods, which were made up basically of milk, cheese and dairy fats (overall OR=1.192; 95% CI: 0.725 – 1.960), and eggs, (overall OR=1.106; 95% CI: 0.594 – 2.059) had the weakest association with STEC infection. At a higher association level laid both seafood – only comprising fish (overall OR=1.546; 95% CI: 0.870 – 2.748) and produce (which were made up of fruits and vegetables; overall OR=1.396; 95% CI: 0.880 – 2.219), although none of them reached statistical significance. Similarly, produce was not an important vehicle of STEC either in young children (overall OR=0.826; 95% CI: 0.543 – 1.255) or in older children (overall OR=0.917; 95% CI: 0.432 – 1.964). Older children were as susceptible to acquire STEC infection through meat consumption (overall OR=2.168; 95% CI: 1.571 – 2.992) as the mixed population (overall OR=2.090; 95% CI: 1.402 – 3.114). However, in young children, meat bore the lowest level risk among the three population classes (overall OR=1.451; 95% CI: 1.105 – 1.904). This may arise from the lower exposure of young children to undercooked meats and processed meats. The meat category comprised ground beef, undercooked beef, meatballs, ham, salami, hamburgers, hotdogs, doner kebab and poultry. The category of dairy products, which included raw milk, ice cream prepared on farm, formula milk and cream cheese, bore a higher mean risk of STEC transmission in young children (overall OR=2.155; 95% CI: 0.812 – 5.720) than in older children (overall OR=1.392; 95% CI: 0.688 – 2.815). Composite foods was found to be a vehicle of transmission of STEC, at least as important as the broad category of meat in the mixed population (overall OR=1.745; 95% CI: 1.104 – 2.759) and older children (overall OR=2.537; 95% CI: 1.485 – 4.332). In young children, composite foods was not found to be significantly associated with disease (overall OR=1.355; 95% CI: 0.859 – 2.138). After Cook’s distance assessment, no potentially-biased OR was removed from the data sets (Table 7B). The formal test for publication bias revealed a strong effect of study size on the measured ORs only for the mixed population (p<.0001). The funnel plots suggested some lack of symmetry, particularly in the mixed population meta-analysis (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of food pathways for STEC infection in the mixed population (top left), young children (top right) and older children (bottom). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Amongst all the food subcategories, meat was the one whose multiple exposures were the most investigated in case-control studies (producing 188 ORs). In all of the geographical areas, meat was an important vehicle for becoming infected with STEC in the mixed population, with pooled OR values ranging from 1.501 (Oceania) to 1.878 (Western Europe; Table 8A). Once again, it was observed that in young children from South America (pooled OR=1.763; $p=0.016$) and Western Europe (pooled OR=1.285; $p=0.039$), the associations with STEC infection, albeit significant, were not as strong as those found for older children from the same regions (pooled OR=2.507 with $p<.0001$ and pooled OR=2.447 with $p<.0001$, respectively). It is believed that young children are the least exposed to meat and meat products, and if they are, undercooked meats would not be an ordinary choice for a meal. Meat was also an important vehicle of transmission of STEC in older children from North America (pooled OR=1.665; $p<.0001$). No data were removed from the meat data partition for adjusting the general meta-analyses by meat class.

Table 8A. Meta-analyses of meat consumption related pathways for STEC infection by region for the mixed population (n=119), young children (n=21) and older children (n=48)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.574	0.124	47	[0.330 – 0.817]	<.0001
North Europe	0.258	0.208	17	[-0.148 – 0.665]	0.213
Oceania	0.406	0.220	30	[-0.025 – 0.836]	0.065
West Europe	0.630	0.194	25	[0.251 – 1.010]	0.001
Young children					
South America	0.567	0.236	4	[0.104 – 1.029]	0.016
West Europe	0.251	0.122	17	[0.013 – 0.489]	0.039
Older children					
North America	0.510	0.133	5	[0.249 – 0.772]	<.0001
South America	0.919	0.145	30	[0.635 – 1.203]	<.0001
West Europe	0.895	0.181	13	[0.540 – 1.250]	<.0001

Within meats, pork consumption bore the lowest risk of STEC infection in the mixed population at a non-significant pooled OR of 0.811 (95% CI: 0.482 – 1.366 in Table 8B). A significantly higher association with disease in the mixed population was found for processed meats, made up of cold/deli meats, ham, sausage rolls, salami, corned beef, bacon, raw spreadable sausage, pre-cooked meat and burger (overall OR=1.526; 95% CI: 1.107 – 2.104). At a higher level of risk laid the consumption of beef (overall OR=1.944; 95% CI: 1.459 – 2.591) which was not significantly different from the “other meats” category encompassing any meat with no specific origin, BBQ meat, donner kebab meat and meat casseroles (overall OR=2.006; 95% CI: 1.432 – 2.809). Interestingly, poultry meat – comprising mostly chicken – presented a higher association with STEC disease than beef/other meats at a pooled OR of 3.370 (95% CI: 1.788 – 6.347 in Table 8B); although it should be kept in mind that only 7 ORs were available. The OR measures for consumption of poultry extracted from four case-control studies were high, ranging from 2.20 to 5.13 and are shown in a forest plot in Figure 10. Very little information was available for the category of other red meats (3 ORs); thus, although its overall mean risk was found to be high (2.654), the high uncertainty about this measure (95% CI: 1.182 – 5.960) did not allow a proper ranking by relative importance among the other meat types.

In the children population, the older ones were more prone to becoming infected with STEC through consumption of beef (pooled OR=2.208; 95% CI: 1.581 – 3.083) than the young ones (pooled OR=1.200; 95% CI: 0.885 – 1.626). However, young children were more likely to acquire STEC infection by consuming processed meats (i.e., raw spreadable sausage and mince meat sausages; overall OR=1.831; 95% CI: 1.093 – 3.065) and other meats (i.e., any meat of unknown origin and doner kebab; overall OR=2.573; 95% CI: 1.440 – 4.600) than older children (i.e., salami and ham at an overall OR=1.514; 95% CI: 0.871 – 2.633; and any raw/undercooked/mince meat of unknown origin at an overall OR=2.114; 95% CI: 1.397 –

3.206; respectively). The consumption of other red meats by young children was not proven to act as a vehicle of STEC (overall OR=1.002; 95% CI: 0.633 – 1.589; Table 8B).

Table 8B. Meta-analyses of meat consumption related pathways for STEC infection for the mixed population (n=119), young children (n=21) and older children (n=48) – no geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (18 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Beef	0.665 ^c	0.146	57	[0.378 – 0.952]	<.0001
	Other red meat	0.976 ^{bcd}	0.413	3	[0.167 – 1.785]	0.018
	Others	0.696 ^c	0.172	20	[0.359 – 1.033]	<.0001
	Pork	-0.209 ^a	0.266	4	[-0.730 – 0.312]	0.432
	Poultry	1.215 ^d	0.323	7	[0.581 – 1.848]	<.0001
	Proc meat	0.423 ^b	0.164	28	[0.102 – 0.744]	0.001
	Before 2000					0.853
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1132	QE(df=113)		QM(df=6)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.5687	p<.0001		p<.0001	
Publication bias	-0.0018	0.0003		<.0001		
Points removed	0					
Young children (3 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Beef	0.182 ^a	0.155	7	[-0.122 – 0.486]	0.240
	Other red meats	0.002 ^a	0.235	4	[-0.458 – 0.463]	0.993
	Others	0.945 ^c	0.296	5	[0.365 – 1.526]	0.001
	Proc meat	0.605 ^b	0.263	5	[0.089 – 1.120]	0.022
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=17)		QM(df=4)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.1263	p=0.983		p=0.002	
	Publication bias	0.0003	0.0012		0.798	
	Points removed	0				
Older children (6 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Beef	0.792 ^b	0.170	36	[0.458 – 1.126]	<.0001
	Others	0.749 ^b	0.212	6	[0.334 – 1.165]	<.0001
	Proc meat	0.415 ^a	0.282	6	[-0.138 – 0.968]	0.141
	Before 2000					ND

Random effects			
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0719	QE(df=44)	QM(df=3)
s^2 (residual)	0.6454	p=0.688	p<.0001
Publication bias	0.0012	0.0005	0.029
Points removed	0		

Figure 10. Forest plot of the meta-analysis conducted on the association of STEC infection in the mixed population with consumption of poultry, as measured by the odds-ratio parameterisation

In the meta-analyses, no potentially-biased observation was removed. According to the publication bias test of study size effect (Table 8B), the sample size of the case-control studies was found to affect the OR measures in the mixed population ($p<.0001$) and the older children population ($p=0.029$; Table 8B). Hence, there is strong evidence that researchers may have been biased to report only the significant ORs arising from meat consumption. Small studies that fail to detect a significant association between meat and STEC infection may have remained unpublished. Funnel plots are shown in Figure 11.

In the questionnaires presented to cases and controls, previous consumption of eggs, seafood was seldom enquired. For this reason, meta-analyses by disaggregated classes could not be conducted on the above subcategories. Since the seafood data partition consisted only of the fish consumption exposure, the pooled OR value already shown in Table 7B is representative of fish only (overall OR=1.547; 95% CI: 0.870 – 2.748, n=6). These OR measures were extracted from case-control studies conducted in Germany, Belgium and UK.

Figure 11. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of meat consumption pathways for STEC infection in the mixed population (top left), young children (top right) and older children (bottom). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The meta-analysis on dairy pathways of transmission by geographical region showed that in Northern Europe, Western Europe and Oceania, there may be only a very weak association, if any, between dairy foods and STEC infection in the mixed population (pooled ORs between 0.661 to 1.220; Table 9A). Young children from Western Europe (pooled OR=7.493; $p=0.001$) were found to be, on average, more susceptible to becoming infected with STEC from consumption of dairy foods than those of South America (pooled OR=1.172; $p=0.524$). However, because of the limited number of OR measures available within this route of exposure, no geographical region was removed for the subsequent meta-analysis by dairy class. On meta-analysis, none of the dairy food classes presented a statistically significant association with STEC infection. In the mixed population, the consumption of cheese (overall OR=1.360; 95% CI: 0.675 – 2.743) or milk (overall OR=1.222; 95% CI: 0.739 – 2.019 in Table 9B) posed a mild risk of disease (OR>1.0). However, the consumption of milk, when raw, by both young children (overall OR=2.762; 95% CI: 0.790 – 9.650) and older children (overall OR=1.402; 95% CI: 0.687 – 2.863) bore a higher mean risk of disease than that of the mixed population. Despite no statistical association between exposure and disease could be encountered for infants consuming milk powder ($p=0.569$), the meta-analysed mean risk was relatively high at OR=1.614 (95% CI: 0.309 – 8.431). There was some evidence of publication bias for the mixed population ($p=0.023$) and older children ($p=0.048$ in Table 9B). Investigating dairy food as a source of STEC transmission is not usual in case-control studies

(Figure 12), and, if examined, it is likely that non-significant ORs would be omitted in the results.

Table 9A. Meta-analyses of dairy consumption related pathways for STEC infection by region for mixed population (n=11) and young children (n=10)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North Europe	-0.414	0.145	4	[-0.698 – -0.130]	0.004
Oceania	0.199	0.286	2	[-0.362 – 0.760]	0.487
West Europe	-0.044	0.262	5	[-0.557 – 0.469]	0.867
Young children*					
South America	0.159	0.250	7	[-0.331 – 0.649]	0.524
West Europe	2.014	0.609	3	[0.821 – 3.208]	0.001

(*) No meta-analysis by region was done for older children since data partition consisted only of 2 ORs from North America and 1 from Western Europe

Table 9B. Meta-analyses of dairy consumption related pathways for STEC infection for mixed (n=12), young children (n=9) and older children (n=3) – no geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed						
(8 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Cheese	0.308 ^a	0.357	6	[-0.392 – 1.009]	0.387
	Milk	0.201 ^a	0.256	6	[-0.302 – 0.703]	0.433
	Before 2000	-0.523	0.297		[-1.105 – 0.059]	0.078
Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2197	QE(df=9)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.5097	p=0.093		p=0.611	
	Publication bias	-0.0014	0.0006			0.023
	Points removed	0				
Young children						
(4 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Raw milk	1.016 ^a	0.638	4	[-0.235 – 2.267]	0.111
	Powder*	0.479 ^a	0.843	5	[-1.173 – 2.132]	0.569
	Before 2000					ND
Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.6752	QE(df=7)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	1.5644	p=0.017		p=0.240	

Publication bias		0.0000	0.0012			0.982
Points removed		0				
Older children (3 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Raw milk**	0.338	0.364	3	[-0.376 – 1.052]	0.354
	Before 2000	ND				
Random effects						
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.1343	QE(df=2)			
	s^2 (residual)	1.5352	p=0.061			
Publication bias		-0.0022	0.0011			0.048
Points removed		0				

(*) Powder is formula milk and bottle left at room temperature for more than 2 hours.

(**) Two ORs for raw milk and one OR for cream cheese

Figure 12. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of dairy consumption related pathways for STEC infection in the mixed population (top left), young children (top right) and older children (bottom). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Meta-analysis did not provide statistical evidence that the consumption of fruits and vegetables would be important vehicle of STEC infection in any of the geographical regions (p-values ranging from 0.237 to 0.894; Table 10A). In Western Europe, produce appeared to pose a lower association with disease (pooled OR=0.834; p=0.582) than in North America (pooled OR=1.660; p=0.237), while in Northern Europe (pooled OR=1.374; p=0.419) and Oceania (pooled OR=1.353; p=0.380) the mean risks of disease were comparable. In children from South America (pooled OR=0.966; p=0.894) and Western Europe (pooled OR=0.850; p=0.437), statistically speaking, produce was not a vehicle of STEC transmission. Because of the limited number of OR measures available within this route of exposure, no geographical region was removed for the subsequent meta-analysis by produce class. Still, data from the mixed and children population were meta-analysed separately.

On average, people who ate vegetables had 1.165 times (95% CI: 0.815 – 2.040) higher probability of acquiring STEC infection than those who did not (Table 10B). Eating fruits bore a slightly higher mean risk in the mixed population (overall OR=1.339; 95% CI: 1.093 – 2.838; Table 10B). From the meta-analysis for (young and older) children, it was found that children who consumed fruits (overall OR=0.977; 95% CI: 0.587 – 1.626) or vegetables (overall OR=0.842; 95% CI: 0.558 – 1.270) were not at risk of acquiring STEC infection. In these meta-analyses, no potentially-biased OR was influential, and publication bias was not evidenced by either the formal test of study size (Table 10B) or the funnel plots (Figure 13).

Table 10A. Meta-analyses of produce consumption related pathways for STEC infection by region for mixed population (n=18) and the combined young (n=5) and older children (n=3) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.507	0.429	3	[-0.334 – 1.348]	0.237
North Europe	0.318	0.393	3	[-0.453 – 1.089]	0.419
Oceania	0.302	0.344	6	[-0.373 – 0.977]	0.380
West Europe	-0.181	0.328	6	[-0.824 – 0.462]	0.582
Young & older children					
South America	-0.035	0.264	3	[-0.552 – 0.482]	0.894
West Europe	-0.162	0.207	5	[-0.568 – 0.246]	0.437

Table 10B. Meta-analyses of produce consumption related pathways for STEC infection for the mixed population (n=18) and the combined young (n=5) and older children (n=3) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (10 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Fruits	0.292 ^b	0.290	7	[0.089 – 1.043]	0.314
	Vegetables	0.153 ^a	0.223	11	[-0.205 – 0.713]	0.495
	Before 2000					0.800
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.2656	QE(df=16)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.7585	p=0.003		p=0.554	
	Publication bias	-0.0006	0.0007			0.411
	Points removed	0				
	Young & older children (4 stud)	Fixed effects				
Fruits		-0.023 ^a	0.260	3	[-0.532 – 0.486]	0.930
Vegetables		-0.172 ^a	0.210	5	[-0.583 – 0.239]	0.412
Before 2000						0.406
Random effects						
s^2_u (Intercept)		0.0000	QE(df=6)		QM(df=2)	
s^2 (residual)		0.1449	p=0.638		p=0.712	
Publication bias		-0.0000	0.0018			0.998
Points removed		0				

Figure 13. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of produce consumption pathways for STEC infection in the mixed population (left) and the combined young and older children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Except for Northern Europe (pooled OR=0.984; p=0.959), composite foods were also important sources of STEC infection in the mixed population from North America (pooled OR=1.536; p=0.037) and Oceania (pooled OR=2.071; p=0.049 in Table 11A). Likewise, children from North America (pooled OR=6.482; p<.0001) and South America (pooled OR=1.610; p=0.001) could as well become infected with STEC from the consumption of composite foods (Table 11A). Due to the limited number of extracted ORs, no geographical region was removed for the general meta-analysis by composite classes.

Table 11A. Meta-analyses of composite-food related pathways for STEC infection by region for the mixed population (n=15) and the combined young children (n=3) and older children (n=9) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.429	0.206	5	[0.025 – 0.833]	0.037
North Europe	-0.016	0.303	4	[-0.608 – 0.577]	0.959
Oceania	0.728	0.370	6	[0.003 – 1.453]	0.049
Young & older children					
North America	1.869	0.475	3	[0.939 – 2.800]	<.0001
South America	0.476	0.138	9	[0.205 – 0.746]	0.001

Analysing the outcomes from general meta-analysis by composite food class, it turned out that young children, as a whole, presented significantly lower risk of acquiring STEC infection through multi-ingredient dishes (overall OR=1.355; 95% CI: 0.859 – 2.138) than the older children population (overall OR=2.883; 95% CI: 1.237 – 6.719), while the mixed population presented only a slightly higher risk (overall OR=1.430; 95% CI: 0.946 – 2.162) than young children (Table 11B). The same trend was observed in the meta-analyses on meats. Young children and infants may be less exposed to multi-ingredient dishes than older children, and when they are, the meals are more carefully prepared and cooked. While dishes in the children population were composed of soup, fried food and desserts, mostly prepared outside the home, the dishes class in the mixed population was made up of desserts, rolls, quiche, macaroni and other multi-ingredient foods, yet all of them prepared outside the home. On meta-analysis, people with STEC infection were on average 1.621 times (95% CI: 0.966 – 2.718) more likely to have consumed any fast-food meal than controls (Table 11B). In the three composite-foods meta-analyses, the observations were unevenly dispersed within the funnel plots, therefore giving some clue for the presence of publication bias (Figure 14). This was corroborated for the significant effects of study size on the OR measures for the mixed population (p=0.013), young children (p=0.056) and older children (p=0.012). No potentially-biased OR was removed from the composite data partition (Table 11B).

Table 11B. Meta-analysis of composite-food related pathways for STEC infection for the mixed population (n=15), young children (n=3) and older children (n=9) – no geographical region was removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (7 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Dishes	0.358 ^a	0.211	12	[-0.055 – 0.771]	0.089
	Fast-food	0.483 ^a	0.264	3	[-0.034 – 1.000]	0.067
	Before 2000					0.351
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.2096	QE(df=13)		QM(df=2)	
	s ² (residual)	0.4395	p<.0001		p=0.120	
	Publication bias	-0.0016	0.0007			0.013
	Points removed	0				
	Young children (all S. A) (1 stud)	Fixed effects				
Dishes		0.304	0.233	3	[-0.152 – 0.760]	0.191
Before 2000						ND
Random effects						
s ² _u (Intercept)		0.0000	QE(df=2)			
s ² (residual)		0.2869	p=0.134			
Publication bias		0.0282	0.0142			0.056
Points removed		0				
Older children (2 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Dishes	1.059	0.432	9	[0.213 – 1.905]	0.014
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.2695	QE(df=8)			
	s ² (residual)	1.0768	p<.0001			
	Publication bias	0.0030	0.0012			0.012
	Points removed	0				

Figure 14. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of composite food consumption pathways for STEC infection in the mixed population (top left), young children (top right) and older children (bottom). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

3.3.3 *Meta-analysis on the risk of STEC infection by ready-to-eat foods and barbecued foods*

As a whole, RTE foods can be regarded as a potential vehicle for transmission of STEC infection in the mixed and children population, as deduced from the integration of the outcomes from case-control studies undertaken in North America (pooled OR=1.542; $p=0.008$ for the mixed population), Oceania (pooled OR=1.809; $p=0.001$ for the mixed population), Western Europe (pooled OR=1.600; $p<.0001$ for the mixed population; and pooled OR=2.351; $p=0.005$ for children) (Table 12A). By contrary, there was no evidence for RTE foods from the UK to be a source of transmission of STEC infection (pooled OR=0.939; $p=0.643$) while the risk in South American children could be only mild (pooled OR=1.339; $p=0.269$).

Table 12A. Meta-analysis of the risk of STEC infection due to consumption of RTE foods by region in the mixed (n=29) and combined children (n=11) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North America	0.433	0.164	6	[0.111 – 0.755]	0.008
North Europe	-0.063	0.135	8	[-0.328 – 0.202]	0.643
Oceania	0.593	0.173	8	[0.254 – 0.932]	0.001
West Europe	0.470	0.122	7	[0.230 – 0.710]	<.0001
Young and older children					
South America	0.292	0.265	6	[-0.226 – 0.811]	0.269
West Europe	0.855	0.303	5	[0.262 – 1.448]	0.005

Table 12B. Meta-analysis of the risk of STEC infection due to consumption of RTE foods overall and by food category in the mixed (n=29) and combined children (n=11) population. No geographical region was removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All RTE foods	0.346	0.112	29	[0.127 – 0.564]	0.002
(10 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Dairy-based	0.237 ^a	0.258	5	[-0.269 – 0.742]	0.359
	Meat-based	0.569 ^b	0.107	24	[0.359 – 0.779]	<.0001
	Before 2000	-0.425	0.147		[-0.713 - -0.139]	0.004
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0007	QE(df=26)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.4650	p=0.067		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0002	0.0004			0.708
	Points removed	0				
Young & older children	All RTE foods	0.544	0.233	11	[0.087 – 1.001]	0.020
(5 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Dairy-based	0.074 ^a	0.293	2	[-0.500 – 0.648]	0.800
	Meat-based	0.668 ^b	0.161	9	[0.354 – 0.983]	<.0001
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=9)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.6049	p=0.040		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0005	0.0012			0.689
	Points removed	0				

The general meta-analysis conducted taking all geographical regions together estimated that people from the mixed population who consumed any RTE food had on average 1.413 (95% CI: 1.135 – 1.758) times greater probability of acquiring STEC infection than those who were not exposed by consumption. Children presented a higher mean risk at an overall OR of 1.722 (95% CI: 1.090 – 2.721; Table 12B). Meta-analysing by RTE class, it was consistently found for both population classes that meat-based RTE foods (including salami, tartare, deli meats, hotdog, ham and processed chicken) bore higher association with STEC disease (overall OR=1.766; 95% CI: 1.432 – 2.179 for the mixed population; and overall OR=1.950; 95% CI: 1.424 – 2.672 for children) than the dairy based RTE foods, which comprised raw milk’s cheese, Brie, cheddar, mozzarella and fromage blanc (overall OR=1.267; 95% CI: 0.764 – 2.100 for the mixed population; and overall OR=1.077; 95% CI: 0.606 – 1.912 for children). In fact, dairy RTE foods did not reach statistical significance in both population classes while meat RTE foods did. Furthermore, children were more susceptible to acquire STEC infection by consumption of meat-based RTE foods than the mixed population. In this data partition, no potentially-biased OR was removed. Results of the formal test for publication bias implied that case-control study size did not affect the measured ORs (p=0.708 for the mixed population, and p=0.689 for children; Table 12B). The lack of publication bias was also supported by the funnel plots, which presented an even spread of data points (Figure 15, top left and right)

With regards to the BBQ meats, only three OR measures were extracted from the literature. The meta-analysis on these three observations indicated that, on average, the consumption of BBQ meats increased the risk of acquiring STEC infection by 1.516 (95% CI: 1.004 – 2.298 in Table 13). As the OR observations were too few, neither Cook’s distance assessment nor formal test for publication bias was carried out. However, for reference, the funnel plot of the BBQ data partition is shown in Figure 15 (bottom).

Table 13. Meta-analysis of the risk of STEC infection due to consumption of BBQ meats by the mixed population (n=3)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Fixed effects (2 stud)					
BBQ meats	0.416	0.212	3	[0.004 – 0.832]	0.050
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=2)			
s^2 (residual)	0.2288	p=0.305			

Figure 15. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of RTE foods as risk factor for STEC infection in the mixed population (top left) and children (top right), and BBQ meats (bottom) as risk factor for STEC infection in the mixed population. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

The main results from the meta-analyses on risk factors and pathways of exposure were compiled in two forest plots: the first forest plot was designed for comparing the association with STEC infection among the *global* risk categories as potential determinants of disease (Figure 16) and the second forest plot for comparing among the *disaggregated* (or more specific) pathways of exposure (Figure 17). To visually distinguish the most important routes of transmission, the pooled ORs listed in the forest plots were ranked by mean's decreasing order, and to assess the reliability in the pooled ORs, the number of ORs used in the computations were displayed.

Examining the global risk categories (Figure 16), the most important route of STEC infection is through person-to-person contagion in the mixed population (overall OR=2.57; 95% CI: 1.44 – 4.59), young children (overall OR=3.12; 95% CI: 1.18 – 8.21) and older children (overall OR=4.55; 95% CI: 1.98 – 10.43), probably followed by travel (overall OR=2.79; 95% CI: 1.53 – 5.10). In the mixed population (as evaluated by means of the mixed only or combined mixed/children partitions), the global animal contact routes (overall OR=2.30; 95% CI: 1.28 – 4.12) and the global host-specific factors (overall OR=2.22; 95% CI: 1.17 – 4.22) were more important determinants of disease than consumption of foods (overall OR=1.75; 95% CI: 1.45 – 2.11). Within foods, the most relevant pathway of transmission of STEC was the meat category (overall OR=2.09; 95% CI: 1.40 – 3.11), which bore as high a risk of

disease as the global environmental routes (overall OR=2.18; 95% CI: 1.76 – 2.71). Following meat, other important vehicles of transmission of STEC infection in the mixed population were: composite foods (overall OR=1.75; 95% CI: 1.10 – 2.76), RTE foods (overall OR=1.41; 95% CI: 1.14 – 1.76) and produce (overall OR=1.40; 95% CI: 0.88 – 2.22).

Figure 16. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring STEC infection for global risk categories, ranked in decreasing order. The global risk categories presented are only those consisting of at least n=3 ORs

On average, young children were more likely to become infected with STEC through environmental pathways (overall OR=2.76; 95% CI: 1.29 – 5.92) and contact with animals (overall OR=1.59; 95% CI: 1.03 – 2.46) than by food (overall OR=1.29; 95% CI: 1.12 – 1.51). Dairy foods (overall OR=2.16; 95% CI: 0.81 – 5.72) turned out to be the most important vehicle for transmission of STEC among the food categories, and bore at least as high an overall risk as the global environmental. The consumption of composite meals by young children (overall OR=1.35; 95% CI: 0.86 – 2.14) was as strong a determinant of disease as the consumption of meat (overall OR=1.45; 95% CI: 1.11 – 1.90). In the older children population, the risk factor landscape was different from that of young children. On average, older children had higher odds of acquiring STEC infection by food consumption (overall OR=1.95; 95% CI: 1.45 – 2.62) than by environmental routes (overall OR=1.69; 95% CI: 1.42 – 2.00). Within the global food categories, composite meals (overall OR=2.54; 95% CI: 1.48 – 4.33) and meat (overall OR=2.17; 95% CI: 1.57 – 2.99) were more important vehicles for transmission of STEC than RTE foods (overall OR=1.72; 95% CI: 1.09 – 2.72) and dairy foods (overall OR=1.39; 95% CI: 0.69 – 2.82). In both young children (overall OR=0.82; 95% CI: 0.54 – 1.25) and older children (overall OR=0.92; 95% CI: 0.43 – 1.94), produce was not an important vehicle of STEC transmission, while in the mixed population, the consumption of dairy (overall OR=1.19; 95% CI: 0.73 – 1.96) and eggs (overall OR=1.11; 95% CI: 0.59 – 2.06) bore a minor risk of disease.

Exploring the disaggregated risk factors (Figure 17), it became evident that, in the mixed population, apart from international travel (overall OR=3.50; 95% CI: 0.99 – 12.35) and domestic travel (overall OR=3.03; 95% CI: 0.96 – 9.54), the most important sources of STEC were consumption of poultry meat (overall OR=3.03; 95% CI: 1.79 – 6.35), living on a farm (overall OR=2.67; 95% CI: 2.18 – 3.27) and person-to-person contagion (overall OR=2.57; 95% CI: 1.44 – 4.59). Some environmental or animal routes of exposure, namely, occupational contact with animals (overall OR=2.48; 95% CI: 1.22 – 5.02), untreated drinking water (overall OR=2.21; 95% CI: 1.68 – 2.89), and contact with farm animals (overall OR=2.11; 95% CI: 1.21 – 3.71) bore higher association with STEC disease in the mixed population than consumption of beef (overall OR=1.94; 95% CI: 1.46 – 2.59) or other non-specific meats (overall OR=2.01; 95% CI: 1.43 – 2.81). After beef, other important routes of exposure to STEC in the mixed population were: recent use of antibiotics (overall OR=1.77; 95% CI: 1.09 – 2.88), meat-based RTE foods (overall OR=1.77; 95% CI: 1.43 – 2.18), handling of manure and bush camping (overall OR=1.71; 95% CI: 1.17 – 2.51), fast foods (overall OR=1.62; 95% CI: 0.97 – 2.72), contact with pets (overall OR=1.59; 95% CI: 0.82 – 3.08), fish (overall OR=1.55; 95% CI: 0.87 – 2.75), processed meats (overall OR=1.53; 95% CI: 1.11 – 2.10), BBQ meats (overall OR=1.52; 95% CI: 1.00 – 2.29), composite dishes (overall OR=1.43; 95% CI: 0.95 – 2.16), cheese (overall OR=1.36; 95% CI: 0.68 – 2.74), fruits (overall OR=1.34; 95% CI=1.09 – 1.64) and recreational water (overall OR=1.31; 95% CI: 1.00 – 1.71).

In older children, the highest association with STEC infection were posed by person-to-person transmission (overall OR=4.55; 95% CI: 1.98 – 10.43) and contact with farm animals (overall OR=3.25; 95% CI: 2.38 – 4.44). The food categories of multi-ingredient dishes (overall OR=2.88; 95% CI: 1.24 – 6.72), beef (overall OR=2.21; 95% CI: 1.58 – 3.08) and other non-specific meats (overall OR=2.11; 95% CI: 1.20 – 3.20) were more important sources of STEC disease than the environmental pathways of living on a farm (overall OR=1.69; 95% CI: 1.35 – 2.12) and drinking untreated water (overall OR=1.61; 95% CI: 1.18 – 2.21). Other important food vehicles of transmission of STEC in older children, following

beef, were meat-based RTE foods (overall OR=1.95; 95% CI: 1.42 – 2.67), processed meats (overall OR=1.51; 95% CI: 0.87 – 2.63) and raw milk (overall OR=1.40; 95% CI: 0.69 – 2.86).

Figure 17. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring STEC infection for disaggregated risk categories, ranked in decreasing order. The disaggregated risk categories presented are only those consisting of at least n=3 ORs

In young children, the top three determinants of STEC infection were living on a farm (overall OR=5.34; 95% CI: 2.51 – 11.36), contact with farm animals (overall OR=4.36; 95% CI: 2.47 – 7.69) and person-to-person contagion (overall OR=3.12; 95% CI: 1.18 – 8.21). Person-to-person and farm environment/animals were also two of the most important sources of STEC in older children and the mixed population. Contrarily to what was found for older children and the mixed population, beef (overall OR=1.20; 95% CI: 0.89 – 1.63) was not an important vehicle of transmission of STEC. Food classes that posed higher risk of infection were raw milk (overall OR=2.76; 95% CI: 0.79 – 9.65), other non-specific meats (overall OR=2.57; 95% CI: 1.44 – 4.60), processed meats (overall OR=1.83; 95% CI: 1.09 – 3.07) and composite dishes (overall OR=1.36; 95% CI: 0.86 – 2.14). Other equally relevant environmental sources of STEC in young children were: exposure to playground (overall OR=2.50; 95% CI: 1.57 – 3.99) and recreational water (overall OR=1.74; 95% CI: 1.04 – 2.93).

Routes of exposure that on meta-analysis had weak (pooled OR marginally higher than one) or non-significant association with STEC infection were: dairy-based RTE (overall OR=1.27; 95% CI: 0.75 – 2.10), milk (overall OR=1.22; 95% CI: 0.74 – 2.02), vegetables (overall OR=1.17; 95% CI: 0.81 – 1.67) and pork meat (overall OR=0.81; 95% CI: 0.48 – 1.37) in the mixed population; attending day care (overall OR=1.25; 95% CI: 0.73 – 2.15), consumption of fruits (overall OR=0.98; 95% CI: 0.59 – 1.63) and vegetables (overall OR=0.84; 95% CI: 0.56 – 1.27) in older children; and contact with pets (overall OR=1.06; 95% CI: 0.72 – 1.56) and consumption of red meats other than beef (overall OR=1.00; 95% CI: 0.63 – 1.59) in young children. Although powder infant formula presented a relatively high mean risk (overall OR=1.61) in young children, its significance as an important vehicle of STEC could not be proven (95% CI: 0.31 – 8.42).

3.3.4 *Meta-analysis on the effects of handling and setting on the risk of transmission of STEC by food consumption*

For some food classes, for which relevant information was available, the effects of handling and setting were appraised. Meta-analysis models were adjusted to data partitions suitable for this analysis: (i) beef, other (non-classifiable) meats and minced meat; (ii) processed meat; (iii) milk. Full estimates and funnel plots are shown in the supplementary Tables S1-S3 and Figures S1-S3. Unlike previous findings on the effects of setting on sporadic salmonellosis and campylobacteriosis, eating out did not come up as a significant factor increasing the risk of acquiring STEC infection. On average, people who ate beef, minced beef and other meats prepared outside the home had their odds of infection only *marginally* increased by 1.108 (95% CI: 0.897 – 1.368 in Table 14) in comparison to the base scenario. In addition, when consuming processed meat, the fact of eating them outside the home did not increase the odds of acquiring STEC infection (OR[Eating out]/OR[Base scenario] = 0.712; 95% CI: 0.428 – 1.184; Table 14).

However, eating undercooked beef/minced beef/other meats was generally a risky practice, as it significantly increased the odds of acquiring STEC infection by 1.466 times (95% CI: 1.219 – 1.766). In other words, people who ate beef/other meats and became infected with STEC had ~1.5 times higher odds to have them consumed raw or undercooked than those who ate beef/other meats but did not get ill. In the case of milk, consuming it without pasteurisation

causes a two-fold increase in the probability of becoming infected with STEC. On meta-analysis, people who affirmed having drunk unpasteurised milk had 2.002 (95% CI: 1.080 – 3.709) greater probability of acquiring STEC infection than those who stated having consumed *simply* milk (without having being specific as to whether it was raw).

Table 14. Meta-analysed effects of handling and setting on base ORs by relevant food class

Food class	Estimate	Mean	2.5 th percentile	97.5 th percentile
Beef, non-classifiable meat and minced meat	OR(Base)	2.166	1.567	2.995
	OR(Undercooked)/OR(Base)	1.466	1.219	1.766
	OR(EatingOut)/OR(Base)	1.108	0.897	1.368
Processed meat	OR(Base)	2.466	1.478	4.112
	OR(EatingOut)/OR(Base)	0.712	0.428	1.184
Milk	OR(Base)	0.800	0.538	1.192
	OR(Raw)/OR(Base)	2.002	1.080	3.709

3.3.5 *Synthesis of the risks associated to ways of preparation and poor handling of foods*

The forest plot of Figure 18 compiles all the exposures related to food preparation and poor food handling practices, which were examined as potential risk factors for sporadic STEC infection in the case-control studies. During preparation of food, having contact with raw fish, raw meat, raw poultry/game or raw vegetables was not proven to increase the risk of acquiring STEC, as suggested by the non-significant ORs between 0.56 and 1.04. However, washing hands after handling raw meats seems to exert a protective effect against STEC infection (ORs 0.57 – 0.60).

Some food preparation practices which are known to generally induce microbial cross-contamination have been proven to increase the odds of acquiring STEC infection, such as: not washing surface (OR=10.50) or hands (OR=8.50) after handling raw ground beef, and using the sample plate for cooked and raw beef (OR=3.30). Other poor habits related to food chilled storage were found to boost the transmission of STEC: leaving raw ground beef out of the fridge for more than 2 hours is a risky practice (OR=1.60), while infants can be exposed to STEC infection if milk bottles are kept at room temperature longer than 2 hours (OR=1.00 – 1.89; Figure 18).

Figure 18. Forest plot of the odds-ratios of acquiring STEC infection associated to food preparation and poor food handling practices

4. Conclusions

4.3 Meta-analysis on risk factors for sporadic STEC infection

- ❖ Five-hundred and three ORs from 29 case-control studies investigating routes of exposure for sporadic STEC infection were meta-analysed, taking into account geographical region, population class and period of study.
- ❖ The top determinants of STEC infection in the mixed population, apart from international travel (OR=3.50) and domestic travel (OR=3.03), are: poultry meat (OR=3.03), living on a farm (OR=2.67) and person-to-person contagion (OR=2.57).
- ❖ The two most important risk factors for transmission of STEC in older children are: person-to-person contagion (OR=4.55) and contact with farm animals (OR=3.25).
- ❖ The top three determinants of STEC infection in young children are: living on a farm (OR=5.34), contact with farm animals (OR=4.36) and person-to-person transmission (OR=3.12).
- ❖ In the mixed population, the animal/environmental routes of occupational contact with animals (OR=2.48), untreated drinking water (OR=2.21), and contact with farm animals (OR=2.11) bear higher association with STEC disease in the mixed population than consumption of beef (OR=1.94) or other non-specific meats (OR=2.01).
- ❖ After beef, other important routes of exposure to STEC in the mixed population are: antibiotics (OR=1.77), meat-based RTE foods (OR=1.77), handling of manure (OR=1.71), fast foods (OR=1.62), contact with pets (OR=1.59), fish (OR=1.55), processed meats (OR=1.53), BBQ meats (OR=1.52), composite dishes (OR=1.43), cheese (OR=1.36), fruits (OR=1.34) and recreational water (OR=1.31).
- ❖ In older children, the food categories of multi-ingredient dishes (OR=2.88), beef (OR=2.21) and other non-specific meats (OR=2.11) are more important sources of STEC disease than the environmental pathways of living on a farm (OR=1.69) and drinking untreated water (OR=1.61).
- ❖ In older children, other important food vehicles of transmission of STEC, following beef, are meat-based RTE foods (OR=1.95), processed meats (OR=1.51) and raw milk (OR=1.40).
- ❖ In young children, beef (OR=1.20) was not an important vehicle of transmission of STEC, unlike older children and the mixed population.

- ❖ In young children, food classes with high association to STEC infection are: raw milk (OR=2.76), other non-specific meats (OR=2.57), processed meats (OR=1.83) and composite dishes (OR=1.36).
- ❖ Other equally relevant environmental sources of STEC in young children were: exposure to playground (OR=2.50) and recreational water (OR=1.74).
- ❖ Eating undercooked beef/minced meat/other meats increases the odds of infection by 1.47 times that of eating beef/minced meat/other meats.
- ❖ Drinking non-pasteurised milk doubles the risk of infection with STEC from consuming milk
- ❖ Eating meats or processed meats prepared outside the home does not increase the risk of STEC infection.
- ❖ Routes of exposure that on meta-analysis had weak or non-significant association with STEC infection are: dairy-based RTE (OR=1.27), milk (OR=1.22), vegetables (OR=1.17) and pork meat (OR=0.81) in the mixed population; day care (OR=1.25), consumption of fruits (OR=0.98) and vegetables (OR=0.84) in older children; and contact with pets (OR=1.06) and consumption of red meats other than beef (OR=1.00) in young children.
- ❖ Very limited data were available for the food subcategories: seafood, eggs, grains and beverages, so the significance of these sources as potential vehicles of transmission of STEC could not be appraised.

5. References

5.3 Twenty-nine case-control studies of STEC infection

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3 Supplementary tables and figures of the effects of handling and setting on the transmission of STEC infection

Table S1. Meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of STEC infection by consumption of beef (n=100) and others (n=31 non-specified meat and mince meat)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Multi					
Handl & Setting: Base	0.773	0.165		[0.449 – 1.097]	<.0001
Handl: Raw or undercook	0.383	0.095	54	[0.198 – 0.569]	<.0001
Setting: Eating out	0.103	0.108	34	[-0.108 – 0.314]	0.340
Uni	-0.385	0.150		[-0.680 – -0.090]	0.010
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0888				
s^2 (residual)	0.6268				
Publication bias	-0.0009	0.0004			0.009
Points removed	0				

Figure S1. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effects of handling and setting on the risk of STEC infection by consumption of beef. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Table S2. Meta-analysis of the effect of setting on the risk of STEC infection by consumption of processed meat (n=36)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
MultiOR					
Setting: Base	0.903	0.261	29	[0.391 – 1.414]	0.001
Setting: Eating Out	-0.339	0.259	7	[-0.848 – 0.169]	0.191
UniOR	-0.624	0.265		[-1.143 – -0.106]	0.018
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0178	QE(df=33)			
s^2 (residual)	0.3285	p=0.291			
Publication bias	-0.0006	0.0003			0.029
Points removed	0				

Figure S2. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effect of setting on the risk of STEC infection by consumption of processed meat

Table S3. Meta-analysis of the effect of handling on the risk of STEC infection by consumption of milk (n=12)

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Handl: Base	-0.223	0.202	4	[-0.620 – 0.175]	0.272
Handl: Raw	0.694	0.315	8	[0.077 – 1.311]	0.027
Random effects					
s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0524	QE(df=10)			
s^2 (residual)	1.3497	p=0.054			
Publication bias	-0.0019	0.0007			0.009
Points removed	0				

Figure S3. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of the effect of handling on the risk of STEC infection by consumption of milk. Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias